

Appendix A: Spectra of L1448N

Figure A.1 shows spectra extracted from the IRS3A and IRS3B continuum peak positions of all transitions (Table 1). The spatial morphology of all transitions within the FoV is presented in Fig. 2.

Appendix B: Outflow morphology of L1448N and L1448-mm

The two NOEMA pointings toward L1448N reveal extended CO and SiO emission that are not only caused by the IRS3A and IRS3B outflows, but there are also contributions by the nearby L1448-mm and IRS3C protostellar outflows. Figure B.1 shows the low-velocity outflow components of CO (2 – 1) in red and blue contours of the L1448N mosaic (Fig. 3) in comparison to the PRODIGE observations toward L1448-mm. A detailed analysis of the L1448-mm data will be presented in future work.

Appendix C: Kinematic analysis of DCN, HC₃N, and CH₃OH

In Sect. 3.4.1, we fit the observed spectra for DCN, HC₃N, and CH₃OH with up to three Gaussian velocity components. Example spectra at several positions (positions are marked in pink in Fig. 6) along the gas bridge and corresponding multi-component Gaussian fits are presented in Fig. C.1.

For DCN (3 – 2), the velocity component at $\approx 5.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is associated with cluster 2, while the component at $\approx 5.9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is connected to the red part of the gas bridge (cluster 4, Fig. 7). The weak emission peak at a velocity of 4.1 km s^{-1} is discarded in the clustering process with DBSCAN. For HC₃N (24 – 23) the component at $\approx 5.6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is connected to the redshifted part of the gas bridge (cluster 4, Fig. C.2). For CH₃OH, the velocity at 5.5 km s^{-1} is associated with the envelope of IRS3B (cluster 2), while the velocity at narrower velocity component at 5.0 km s^{-1} is connected to the blueshifted side of the gas bridge (cluster 3, Fig. C.2).

The velocity components derived from the multi-component Gaussian modeling are clustered into their underlying physical origin using DBSCAN (Sect. 3.4.2). While the velocity clusters of DCN are shown in Fig. 7, the results for the HC₃N and CH₃OH are presented in Fig. C.2. The corresponding amplitude and line width maps are shown in Figs. C.3 and C.4, respectively.

The velocity gradients of the gas bridge are discussed in Sect. 4.1.1. The velocity gradient map of DCN is shown in Fig. 8, while the results for HC₃N and CH₃OH are shown in Figs. C.5 and C.6, respectively. The input and results from the clustering with DBSCAN and the global velocity gradients of each part of the gas bridge are summarized in Table C.1.

Fig. A.1. Spectra toward the continuum peak positions of IRS3A (black) and IRS3B (red). The blue dash-dotted line marks the $3\sigma_{\text{line}}$ level (σ_{line} is listed in Table 1 for all transitions). The green vertical dashed lines mark the velocity integration range, v_{low} and v_{upp} (Table 1), used to compute the moment 0 maps (Fig. 2).

Table C.1. Kinematic properties of DCN (3 – 2), HC₃N (24 – 23), and CH₃OH (4_{2,3} – 3_{1,2}E).

Transition	Velocity components	DBSCAN input			DBSCAN results			Global velocity gradient (km s ⁻¹ pc ⁻¹)
	$n_{\text{Gauss,max}}$	data points (x,y,v)	eps	minsamples	cluster	clustered data points	discarded	
DCN	3	2856	0.30	95	$n_{\text{cluster,tot}} = 4$	1999	857	
red bridge					cluster 4	647		52
blue bridge					cluster 3	542		77
HC ₃ N	1	545	0.208	20	$n_{\text{cluster,tot}} = 4$	466	79	
red bridge					cluster 4	126		116
blue bridge					cluster 1	61		131
CH ₃ OH	2	1962	0.280	75	$n_{\text{cluster,tot}} = 4$	1500	462	
red bridge					cluster 4	106		52
blue bridge					cluster 3	606		69

Notes. $n_{\text{Gauss,max}}$ is the maximum number of velocity components per spectrum in the Gaussian decomposition (Sect. 3.4.1). The clustering method using DBSCAN is described in Sect. 3.4.2 and the global velocity gradient is the average gradient among the velocity gradient maps presented in Figs. 8, C.5, and C.6.

Fig. B.1. The same as the left panel in Fig. 3, but including the PRODIGE observations of the nearby L1448-mm protostar.

Fig. C.1. Examples of observed spectra and Gaussian decomposition. The observed spectra are shown in black (top: DCN, middle: HC₃N, and bottom: CH₃OH) and are extracted from bridge positions (Fig. 6) marked in the upper right. The total fit is indicated by the solid red line, while individual Gaussian velocity components are shown by the red dashed lines. The source velocity of IRS3A and IRS3B are indicated by the dashed grey and orange line, respectively. The line noise ($\pm 5\sigma_{\text{line}}$, Table 1) are indicated by horizontal dashed green lines.

Fig. C.2. The same as Fig. 7, but for HC_3N (top panel) and CH_3OH (bottom panel).

Fig. C.3. The same as Fig. 7, showing the corresponding peak intensity I_{peak} of the velocity clusters for DCN (top panel), HC_3N (middle panel) and CH_3OH (bottom panel).

Fig. C.4. The same as Fig. 7, showing the FWHM line width Δv of the velocity clusters for DCN (top panel), HC_3N (middle panel) and CH_3OH (bottom panel).

Fig. C.5. The same as Fig. 8, but for HC_3N (24 – 23).

Fig. C.6. The same as Fig. 8, but for CH₃OH (4_{2,3} – 3_{1,2}E).